

INTERDISCIPLINARY ABCISSIONAL AND ORDINAL VISUAL ASSIGNMENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL MATH CLASSES AS A MAJOR FACTOR IN PUPILS DEVELOPING THEIR CREATIVE THINKING

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Annotation. The article explores the fact that interdisciplinary abscissional and ordinal visual assignments in primary school mathematics classes are the basis for students' development of creative thinking.

Keywords: creative thinking, problem, principle, logic, perception, ability, memory, attitude, reflection.

Creative concepts and approaches have fueled the development of human culture in various regions of the world. Therefore, creative thinking is very different from just random thoughts. It is considered a real competence based on knowledge and experience, which allows people to achieve expected results in tense and complex situations. Organizations and societies around the world are focusing on the acquisition of innovative ideas, knowledge and skills to overcome the emerging complexities, looking to innovative ideas and creative thinking as a shared initiative.

The study of the problems related to the didactic foundations of the formation of mathematical creative thinking in primary school pupils by interdisciplinary abscissional and ordinate connection showed that it was not a special subject of research works of other authors and was not studied in detail, only some issues of this problem were considered. Although it is very relevant, it has been partially worked out, and the didactic foundations of forming the mathematical creative thinking of primary school pupils by interdisciplinary abscissional and ordinate connection have not been sufficiently studied.

Analyzing various approaches to solving the problems of forming mathematical creative thinking in primary school pupils in psychology and pedagogy literature, the following descriptions were determined in the course of research: mathematical creative thinking is an important component of the general creative thinking of a person; mathematical creative thinking has features related to mathematical methods of knowing real existence and the uniqueness of its reflection in mathematics, and mathematical creative thinking has a complex and multi-level structure. Important characteristics that determine the level of formation and development of mathematical creative thinking include: ability to perceive, imagine and assimilate knowledge,

mathematical ingenuity, intelligence, memory strength; the ability to determine the relationship between quantitative quantities and relationships; relying on mathematical images, concepts and ideas; ability to reflect; strengthening of ideas about speech [1].

The ability to perceive, imagine and acquire knowledge means the ability to spatial imagination and perception, abstraction, mental images and the ability to use special forms of thinking [2;4].

Relying on mathematical images, concepts and considerations means the ability to formally accept materials related to mathematics, to acquire mathematical knowledge, skills, skills and competencies relatively quickly and deeply, to improve flexible mental operations, to solve problems describing specific practical problems [5, 6], to develop skills it is appropriate to solve the issues in the following form:

Issue 1. 300 kg of flour is packed in bags of 5 kg and 10 kg. If there are an equal amount of 5 kg and 10 kg of bags, how many bags of flour are in it?

Answer: 40 of them

When pupils think creatively about problems, their mathematical thinking improves, and the flexibility of concrete ideas develops.

The ability to reflect is understood as theoretical activity aimed at understanding actions and laws, self-knowledge, relying on interrelated logical operations, independence and self-control, understanding induction and deduction methods and their correct application [3].

Issue. Three-digit numbers can be formed from the numbers on three cards. For example, 524, 254. How many three-digit numbers can be formed in total?

Answer: at most 6 numbers can be generated.

It was determined that the following are considered important aspects of pedagogical activities that allow the formation of mathematical creative thinking of primary school pupils through interdisciplinary abscissional and ordinate connections: creation of motivation to study; organization of independent thinking activities of primary school pupils; organization of joint activities and communication; use of the principle of gradual formation of mental actions in educational activities.

It was justified that the educational technologies used in the formation of creative thinking of primary school pupils by interdisciplinary abscissional and ordinate connection should be based on the following principles: individualization of education; knowledge integration; educational

systematization; educational informatization; interactive education, problem-based education.

Methods of mental activity include generalization, abstraction and clarification of mental imagination and creative thinking methods. The method of generalization from the particular to the general (with the inductive method), for example, can be carried out in the following order: a) comparing the studied subjects; b) display and identify all signs common to objects; c) combine objects according to their common features [6].

In the case where generalization is done in a didactic way (from general to specific), primary school pupils should be able to choose the specific concept being studied from among the general concepts and to be able to state its general features. Consciously transferring concepts to find a solution to the task at hand serves as an indicator of mastering the method of mental activity.

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